

Supplementary information

Exploring climate-induced sex-based differences in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems to mitigate biodiversity loss

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Table S1. Examples of sex-based responses to climate change at different levels of biological organization.

Sex-specific growth and maturation in response to changing climate	Sources
a. Sex-specific growth and maturation of fish populations in response to changing climate. 1988/9 climate regime shift had pervasive effects on female and male maturation schedules and growth in Korean chum salmon (<i>Oncorhynchus keta</i>) population, with different maturation trends between males and females, a decrease in body size and an increase in age at spawning in females. These changes have affected the reproductive success of spawning males and females.	Ref. ¹
b. Sex-specific growth and maturation of Arctic wolf spiders. Climate change is advancing the onset of the growing season and this is happening at a particularly fast rate in the High Arctic. However, in most species the relative fitness implications for males and females remain elusive. By studying data on 10 successive cohorts of the wolf spider <i>Pardosa glacialis</i> from Zackenberg in High-Arctic, northeast Greenland, Høye et al. ² found marked inter-annual variation in adult body size (carapace width) and this variation was greater in females than in males. Earlier snowmelt during both years of its biennial maturation resulted in larger adult body sizes and a skew towards positive sexual size dimorphism (females bigger than males). These results illustrate the pervasive influence of climate on key life-history traits and indicate that male and female responses to climate should be investigated separately whenever possible.	Refs. ^{2,3}
Sex-specific thermal performance	
c. Sex-specific thermal performance of copepods in response to climate change. In two populations of copepods <i>Acartia tonsa</i> from Connecticut and Florida (US), males showed significantly lower survival than females when exposed to increasing temperatures. Ignoring sex-specific differences in thermal tolerance may lead to underestimating population decline due to sperm limitation.	Ref. ⁴

<p>d. Sex-specific thermal performance of flying foxes in response to thermal extremes. Welbergen et al.⁵ examined the effects of temperature extremes on behaviour and demography of vulnerable wild flying-foxes (<i>Pteropus spp.</i>) in New South Wales, Australia. In 2002 temperatures exceeding 42°C killed over 3500 individuals in nine mixed-species colonies. Young and adult females were more affected than adult males (young, 23–49%; females, 10–15%; males, less than 3%). Such differences have been reported to cause severe sex ratio distortion in some natural populations, such as in tropical black flying foxes where 84% of adults killed by an extreme high-temperature event were females.</p>	Ref. ⁵
<p>Sex-specific energetic bottlenecks in response to climate-induced change</p>	
<p>e. Sex-specific caloric intake of Pacific walrus in response to climate-induced sea ice reduction. Increased the time active in water may result in negative energy balance in female walrus (<i>Odobenus rosmarus divergens</i>) that precludes them from sustaining lactation, impacting their capacity to reproduce, and limiting adequate nutrition for offspring, potentially reducing juvenile survival - a development that may impact overall walrus population demographics and survival. Females rely on the presence of sea ice to give birth and nurse their calves. They migrate annually to the ice edge through the fall, they breed in winter and return to the Bering Sea in spring. On the contrary, males are less dependent on sea-ice cover. Their haul-out locations are prominent throughout the year along ice-free portions of the Bearing Sea and in the southeast Bering Sea in open water conditions. As a consequence of the shift to terrestrial haul-outs and of the likely increase of exposure to anthropogenic stressors, an unusually high mortality rate was observed in walrus in coastal Alaska and Russia in 2007 and 2009⁶ especially of juveniles being trampled⁷. The autumn retreat of sea ice to the north of the continental shelf has become a common occurrence, and so the use of terrestrial haul-outs for females.</p>	Refs. ^{8–12} , 13,14
<p>f. Sex-specific foraging strategy of Caribous facing climate-induced snow cover reduction. Caribous experience nutritional deficiencies in the calving season. Lactating females have higher daily food intake, forage longer than non-reproductive females, and prioritize quality (i.e., high nitrogen) feed. Foraging strategies of lactating females will be probably altered facing climate change. Females can migrate northward to enhance high quality forage but increase the risk of predation. As an alternative strategy, females can forage longer to compensate for the decrease of forage quality, but increasing insect harassment in warmer climate. Overall, reduced forage quality might have a negative impact on caribou fitness and population growth.</p>	Refs. ^{15,16}
<p>Sex-specific effects of climate change on population demography</p>	
<p>g. Sex-specific effects of fisheries and climate on the demography of sexually dimorphic birds. In Southern Atlantinc northern (<i>Macronectes halli</i>) and southern (<i>M. giganteus</i>) giant petrels females are more sensitive to increases in fishing effort, variation in oceanographic conditions and sea ice concentration. Males, by contrast, are more sensitive to land-based carrions. Ignoring sex-based differences could underestimate the relative influence of a changing environment on population survival and reduce the effectiveness of conservation strategies.</p>	Ref. ¹⁷
<p>h. Sex ratio altered by temperature change in reptiles. Changes in environmental temperature can profoundly alter the sex ratio of temperature-dependent sex determination species. Environmental conditions experienced during embryonic development have population-scale consequences in taxa for which offspring sex is irreversibly determined by thermal regimes experienced during development¹⁸, such as reptiles¹⁸, amphibians¹⁹, and birds²⁰. Equal numbers of male and female offspring are produced at a pivotal temperature, whereas higher or lower ambient temperatures result in consistent sex ratio bias²⁰ with increasing temperatures leading to more females in hatchling sex ratios in sea turtles^{21–23} and more males in tuatara (<i>Sphenodon guntheri</i>)²⁴. Understanding sex ratios is indeed essential for conservation management effectiveness. In the case of sea turtles, knowledge of females through flipper tagging and satellite tracking studies is abundant since females predictably appear on nesting beaches where researchers can tag them^{23,25,26}. Knowledge of male turtles movement, by contrast, is limited as males rarely come on-shore and tagging them offshore is difficult and costly^{23,27–29}. Knowing more about male sea turtles is essential, particularly in light of the rapid increase in females in sea turtle populations due to global warming^{22,23}.</p>	(various)
<p>Effects on sex change</p>	
<p>i. High temperature-induced sex reversal in amphibians. Temperature-induced sex reversal refers to cases in which sex is initially determined genetically, but is then altered by environmental temperature³⁰. Mikò et al.³¹ found female-to-male sex-reversing effects of high temperature in agile frogs (<i>Rana dalmatina</i>). High temperature induced female-to-male sex reversal, decreased survival, delayed</p>	Refs. ^{30,31}

metamorphosis, decreased body mass at metamorphosis, and increased the proportion of animals that had no fat bodies. climate change and chemical pollution may have complex consequences for individual fitness and population persistence in species with environment-sensitive sex determination. The actual fitness effects of sex reversal are incompletely known. For a review on the topic, see ref. ³⁰ .	
j. Shift in timing of sex change in protandrous hermaphrodites. Ocean acidification can affect the timing of the transition from male to female in Arctic Northern shrimps (<i>Pandalus borealis</i>). This will likely affect sex ratio, and may impact Greenland fishery production.	Ref. ³²

Supplementary box S1. Example of a policy implemented in Australia to counteract the effects of the increase in temperature on sea turtle populations.

The Department of Environment and Science of the State of Queensland, Australia, designed the “Queensland marine turtle conservation strategy 2021–2031”³⁸ to counter the impacts of increasing sand temperatures negatively impacting hatchling sex ratio and hatching success of eggs in six species of marine turtles. The conservation strategy consists in implementing practical nest cooling techniques, such as nest shading or egg relocation. The aim is to increase the production of male hatchlings to achieve ecologically appropriate sex ratios in the Great Barrier Reef populations, and to help recover Queensland’s marine turtle stocks in the long term. Although this will be challenging at large spatial scales, the reduced recruitment of sub-adult males could cause a catastrophic stock decline within one generation, impacting more than 30 years of marine turtle conservation efforts. The plan has established the following Target 3.2.: “Nesting success and survivability of marine turtle clutches of eggs and hatchlings is increased to more than 80% with a target sex ratio above 30% male to support long-term stock recovery (the 80% target is higher than in the national Recovery Plan and considered necessary to recover depleted stocks in the face of increasing threats such as climate change).”. To combat this, the department’s researchers used shade cloth to keep the sand temperature cool enough for turtle nests. More than 300 clutches of eggs were relocated to shaded areas of the beach in one nesting season. Sand surface temperatures under the shade cloth were around 30° cooler than on the exposed dunes and the department’s researchers were confident that at nest depth, which is up to 60cm below the sand, temperatures remained lower than the critical 32°. This simple idea makes a real difference to the numbers of hatchling turtles produced at Mon Repos which is critical to the survival of the loggerhead turtle. More than 1300 clutches of eggs hatch in total each nesting season. Mon Repos is of particular importance as a nesting site for the endangered loggerhead turtle, which lays around 125 eggs per clutch. Green turtles and flatbacks also use the rookery, laying 115 eggs and 50 eggs per clutch, respectively.

The conservation strategy includes i) monitoring pivotal temperature – the temperature at which 50% of the hatchlings are female – and nest temperature at local conditions for the different populations and ii) testing management actions effectiveness. Monitoring protocols in marine protected areas have been updated to include sex-specific considerations.

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